

GREAT Case Study GCS5

Play2Act

Work Package: WP4: GCS3 Case Study Play2Act

Grant Agreement Number: 101094766

Due date of deliverable: 2025

Actual completion date: June 2025

Start date of project: 01/02/2023 (36 months)

Dissemination Level: public (PU)

Deliverable Lead: UoB

Author(s): Rebecca Harris (r.harris@bolton.ac.uk), Paul Hollins (p.a.hollins@bolton.ac.uk), Jude Ower (jude.ower@planetplay.com),

Joost Schuur (joost.schuur@planetplay.com)

Point of Contact: Hendrik Drachsler

Deliverable Information

Reviewers	<Name> <E-mail>, <Name> <E-mail> & <Name> <E-mail>
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	Click or tap here to enter text.
Keywords	Case Study, Games, Climate
Statement of originality	<p>This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.</p> <p>Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.</p>

Document History

Version	Date	Comment (Examples)
0.1	Click or tap to enter a date.	Draft 0.1 document created
0.2	31 January 2025	Final draft completed
0.3	Click or tap to enter a date.	Peer review and detailed feedback on overall structure and specific content
0.4	Click or tap to enter a date.	Integration of peer review comments and final editing
1.0	Click or tap to enter a date.	Document complete and submitted

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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

The Play2Act case study builds upon the GCS1 Exploratory study by validating the integration of digital surveys into gaming environments as a tool for large-scale public engagement and policy research. By collaborating with multiple game studios, Play2Act successfully reached over 934,000 players from 228 countries, embedding surveys into popular gaming platforms. This method proved effective for gathering data on climate change attitudes, demonstrating the potential of digital games to reach diverse global audiences and generate high engagement.

The study's findings highlight the effectiveness of gaming as a research tool. With a 90.7% response rate, Play2Act showed games can overcome traditional barriers in public engagement, such as geographical and literacy limitations. However, while the surveys provided valuable insights into climate awareness and behavioural intentions, the study also identified challenges, particularly in terms of demographic representation and participant engagement depth. Future research should focus on integrating survey content within active gameplay to enhance participant reflection and engagement, and on improving the representativeness of data, especially in underrepresented groups.

Although Play2Act demonstrated promising results in engaging players on climate change, it revealed that smaller behavioural shifts, such as changes in daily habits, were more common than larger, more impactful actions. This suggests digital interventions should complement policy changes to drive more significant societal impacts. Additionally, the study raised questions about the extent to which gaming environments foster deeper climate policy literacy, with participants showing limited knowledge of specific policies despite engaging with environmental content.

Play2Act provides valuable insights into the potential of digital games as research tools. While it successfully engaged a large, diverse audience, challenges in dataset representativeness, engagement depth, and long-term behaviour change remain. Future research should explore how digital games can more directly integrate educational content, encourage sustained behaviour change, and strengthen their role in policy discourse.

2. Introduction

Climate change is a critical global challenge with wide-ranging impacts on sustainability, economy, and society. As temperatures rise and extreme events increase, innovative strategies are needed to engage the public in meaningful climate action. While traditional approaches to climate communication, such as public awareness campaigns and educational initiatives, have achieved some success, they often struggle to resonate with younger generations who are more engaged with digital media and interactive entertainment.

The Play2Act case study uses the immersive nature of video games to engage players with climate issues. By integrating environmental content within gaming experiences, it explores how gaming platforms can raise climate awareness and encourage real-world action. With the gaming industry's broad reach, this approach offers a unique way to assess whether digital environments can educate players and drive behavioural change. The case study contributes to discussions on digital engagement in climate action, examining the effectiveness of in-game messaging and its impact on player attitudes and intentions, highlighting the potential of digital gamification for social and environmental change.

Play2Act, developed in collaboration with the UNDP, supports global climate action through initiatives such as the Climate Promise and aligns with the UNDP's mission to help countries meet their climate commitments under the Paris Agreement. Building on the success of previous initiatives such as Mission 1.5, Play2Act refines the survey-based approach by embedding climate-related surveys directly into gaming environments, avoiding the use of playable ads. While Mission 1.5 engaged millions with a gamified experience, Play2Act tests an alternative methodology to improve response quality and maintain large-scale reach. The study aims to assess how digital engagement can influence citizen participation in social issues and inform policymakers about public attitudes, contributing to the ongoing role of games in civic participation and policy engagement. The study used an innovative approach by embedding climate-related survey questions within popular games, enabling access to demographics often overlooked by traditional climate communication. This method integrated environmental engagement seamlessly into familiar platforms, reducing participation barriers and improving accessibility. By collecting extensive global survey responses, the study provides valuable insights and best practices for game developers and policy stakeholders on integrating research tools into digital entertainment.

Play2Act also examined the broader implications of using games to address societal challenges, weighing the benefits and risks for individuals and society. It demonstrated the potential of gaming platforms for large-scale engagement while ensuring ethical, data governance, and design considerations were rigorously addressed. By integrating knowledge, sentiment, and behaviour change questions within the gaming ecosystem, Play2Act provided a model for using

interactive entertainment to inform global policy discussions, with potential applications beyond climate change.

3. Methodology

The Play2Act case study utilised a quantitative approach, combining in-game surveys with data collection to assess player engagement with climate-related content in digital games. The goal was to determine whether this engagement increased awareness and intent to act on environmental issues. Surveys were embedded in widely played mobile games participating in the Playing for the Planet initiative, which integrates sustainability themes. Game studios involved aimed to gather data to refine their approach to incorporating environmental messaging within their platforms.

Surveys were integrated into the gaming ecosystem using each platform's existing communication tools, ensuring organic and non-intrusive player engagement. Instead of embedding surveys directly into gameplay, games utilised their established messaging or advertising systems to reach players, although the case study did not assess the extent to which they may have disrupted gameplay. As demonstrated in image 1, some games used news or messaging sections, while others employed overlays at game launch, for example, in Pokémon GO, Niantic leveraged its in-game advertising system to promote the survey, providing a controlled, scalable distribution method that aligned with existing player engagement patterns while maintaining a seamless experience.

Image 1: Visualisations of Play2Act Survey Promotion

The Play2Act surveys engaged 933,852 players across 228 countries, including 188 UN-recognised nations. The primary data collected was quantitative, focusing on demographics, climate awareness, and self-reported behavioural intentions regarding sustainability. This enabled the identification of engagement patterns, attitude shifts, and potential links between in-game climate messaging and real-world intentions. A total of 204,796 respondents answered at least one question, yielding a 90.7% response rate. Among engaged users, 77.2% completed the survey, and 181,087 players finished it, resulting in a 15.2% overall completion rate. Participants were offered a reward in the form of a discount on a PlanetPlay marketplace purchase, with a portion supporting sustainability initiatives. While 26.5% of non-Xbox Insider participants created marketplace accounts to redeem the reward, this did not confirm continued engagement, and the dataset does not track long-term involvement.

This case study demonstrates the potential of large-scale digital games as tools for collecting behavioural and attitudinal data. It demonstrates how digital engagement can effectively address social and environmental issues. The targeted placement strategy within Pokémon GO provides valuable insights for future research using high-reach platforms for data collection and assessing social impact.

Ethical Considerations:

The case study adhered to rigorous ethical standards, ensuring informed consent from all participants. Players were made aware that their responses would be collected for research purposes, and their anonymity was guaranteed. Ethical protocols were followed in ensuring that participants were not coerced into providing feedback, and that their responses would be used solely for the purposes of the research.

3.1 Mapping of RQ’s to Case Study

Table 1. Mapping of research questions to the case study

Revised research objectives and questions	<i>Simple formulation in terms of GREAT</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>
Objective 1. Establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policymakers.		
RQ1.1 Which methods in digital games can be used to create an information exchange between attitudes and preferences of citizens on societal challenges (e.g.,	<i>How can GREAT be achieved?</i>	YES

climate change) and policy makers working on these challenges?		
RQ1.2 How effective and efficient is the use of games in creating an information exchange between attitudes and preferences of citizens on societal challenges (e.g. climate change) and policy makers?	<i>Does GREAT do what we want it to do?</i>	NO
RQ1.3 How can games be used to foster dialogue and collaboration on societal challenges (e.g. climate change)?	<i>How much work is it to use the GREAT approach?</i>	YES
Objective 2. Understand the actual and potential impact that games can have on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges, and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes and preferences.		
RQ2.1 What are the affordances of games in developing citizens' engagement with challenges and dilemmas arising from societal challenges like climate crisis?	<i>What is it about GREAT that makes it good for gathering and representing opinions and attitudes?</i>	NO
RQ2.2 What are the affordances of games in informing policy on the societal challenges like climate crisis?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for policy stakeholders and policy makers?</i>	YES
RQ2.3 What is the value to policy stakeholder groups of the information on citizens' attitudes and preferences generated through games-based activities?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for citizens?</i>	NO
RQ 2.4: What is the value to citizens of enabling them to engage in policy discourse through the design of and engagement in games-based activities?	<i>What do people gain by using games to discuss policy?</i>	YES

RQ 2.5: How generalisable are the GREAT methods to other global challenges or other fields of research and innovation?	<i>How well can the GREAT methods apply to other global challenges?</i>	YES
Objective 3. Provide practical guidance for games developers and policy stakeholders.		
RQ 3.1: Which are the key interventions in the GREAT method which lead to its effectiveness and efficiency?	<i>Which parts of the GREAT method make it work well and efficiently?</i>	NO
RQ 3.2: Which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting the method to new contexts?	<i>Which key factors matter when adapting the method to different contexts?</i>	YES
RQ 3.3: What documentation and/or training is required for games developers, policy stakeholder groups?	<i>Which training or information do developers and policy groups need?</i>	YES
Objective 4. Assess the benefits and risks to individuals and society of using games to promote engagement with societal challenges.		
RQ 4.1: What are the benefits and risks experienced by citizen participants, policy stakeholders, games designers and providers, as well as policy makers and organisations, when they participate in the GREAT method?	<i>What are the benefits and risks for citizens, policy-makers, and game teams using the GREAT method?</i>	NO

3.2 Detailing the design process for the case study

Table 2. Detailing the design process for the case study

Step of Case Study Cycle	Overview of the Eight-Step Cycle <i>Provide a brief description of each step in the case study process.</i>
<p>Create and Prioritise Research Topics (Step 1)</p> <p><i>Document the outcomes of initial workshops.</i></p>	<p>The Play2Act case study was developed as part of the GREAT project, aligning with its broader objective of exploring digital games as a medium for citizen engagement and policymaker interaction. The research focused on how in-game activities could facilitate discourse on climate change, providing policymakers with insights into public attitudes and preferences. Central to this phase was defining the overarching research questions, which sought to examine the methods through which digital games could foster an exchange of information between citizens and policymakers, the effectiveness of such approaches, and their broader applicability to societal challenges beyond climate change. This phase also involved establishing a methodological foundation by validating the approach trialled in GCS1 UNDP Exploratory, ensuring that it could be effectively scaled for larger datasets.</p>
<p>Collaborate in Study Design (Step 2)</p> <p><i>Describe the collaborative case study design process.</i></p>	<p>While the core survey content and system functionality were primarily designed by the research team, the implementation process required careful negotiation to align the study’s objectives with the commercial and creative considerations of participating studios. Studios were selected due to their participation in the Playing for the Planet initiative. The game studios involved were interested in gathering data to understand player engagement with environmental messaging and to refine their approach to embedding sustainability themes within their platforms.</p> <p>The study design was structured around a large-scale in-game survey, strategically embedded within various digital games to capture player responses at scale. Given the constraints imposed by the gaming environment, the survey was deliberately limited to closed-ended questions, prioritising quantitative data collection while acknowledging the absence of qualitative insights as a limitation. Additionally, technical and legal considerations, such as data protection and intellectual property rights, were addressed to facilitate smooth implementation across multiple studios.</p>

<p>Collaborate in Design of Games-Based Activities (Step 3)</p> <p><i>Explain the collaborative design of game activities.</i></p>	<p>Unlike traditional surveys, which rely on external recruitment and participation, this study leveraged the immersive nature of digital games to engage players organically. Surveys were integrated into gaming ecosystems before active play, while participation remained voluntary, the placement within familiar in-game interfaces encouraged seamless interaction, leveraging existing engagement patterns rather than interrupting the gaming experience.</p> <p>The design process accommodated studio preferences regarding how the survey was promoted within their games, aligning with each platform’s existing communication capabilities. While studios retained autonomy over the specific placement and framing of survey links, these decisions were based on their standard engagement tools rather than an iterative co-design process. In most cases, studios integrated the survey using their established messaging or advertising systems, with minimal need for adjustments. The only exception was a scenario where one studio preferred not to link to an external survey, prompting the addition of a redirect function to return players to the game post-completion. Despite the high engagement this flexibility allowed, one of the key limitations noted was the inability to incorporate open-ended responses, which could have provided deeper qualitative insights into player attitudes and motivations.</p>
<p>Piloting and Gathering Data (Step 4) - PILOT & TEST</p> <p><i>Document the piloting phase and data collection.</i></p>	<p>Piloting was conducted early in 2024 within GCS1 UNDP1 Exploratory, which used a QR code in the main menu of the game SMITE, alongside some Meta Ads, but these ads were not directly in the gaming interface. More detail on this can be found in GCS1 UNDP1 Case Study Report.</p> <p>The data collection phase in Play2Act spanned from October 1, 2024, to January 31, 2025, during which the survey was embedded in various games across different geographic regions. Once live, the survey garnered an exceptional response rate, with over 181,087 completed surveys and low dropout rates after the first page. The engagement levels varied across games, influenced by</p>

	factors such as game genre, player demographics, and the nature of the in-game prompts.
<p>Data Interpretation and Outcomes (Step 5) <i>Analyse and interpret the data collected.</i></p>	<p>The collected data was processed, Python used for data preparation, and SPSS and Pandas in Python utilised for statistical analysis, allowing for comprehensive statistical interpretation. Initial analysis revealed significant trends in player attitudes towards climate change, with variations based on age, gender, and education level. The findings also demonstrated the potential of in-game surveys to provide large-scale, real-time insights into public opinion, a capability that is often difficult to achieve through conventional survey methodologies. While the study successfully captured quantitative trends, the absence of open-ended responses limited the depth of interpretation, particularly regarding the motivations behind player attitudes and behavioural changes following exposure to climate-related content.</p> <p>Studios were given access to anonymised insights, which informed their own climate-related content strategies and player engagement models.</p>
<p>Conclusions and Outputs (Step 6) <i>Summarise conclusions and recommendations.</i></p>	<p>The Play2Act case study produced several key conclusions reinforcing the viability of using digital games as a research tool for policymaking. While the case study confirmed in-game surveys can yield high engagement rates and reliable data collection at scale, suggesting games are an effective medium for gathering public input on complex social issues, the case study highlighted logistical challenges, particularly in managing multi-stakeholder collaborations, aligning studio timelines with research objectives, and navigating legal and ethical considerations related to data collection. Based on these findings, future development could focus on automating survey integration through a data-driven trigger system, reducing manual workload and supporting broader industry adoption. Further technical analysis is needed to assess feasibility and refine its implementation.</p>
<p>Public Engagement and Dissemination of Outcomes (Step 7) <i>Outline strategies for disseminating findings.</i></p>	<p>The Play2Act study's results were shared through various channels, including 11 calls with game studios from November 2024 to January 2025 and a major UNDP call in January. Game studios received aggregate raw data to support their own analyses. In</p>

	<p>March 2025, UNDP began preparing a press release summarising key findings, with further discussions on presenting results interactively on the UNDP Data Futures site.</p> <p>Future dissemination plans include academic publications, industry white papers, and conference presentations. The case study serves as a model for using digital games in large-scale data collection, with potential applications beyond climate change to areas like public health, governance, and social justice.</p> <p>Top-level findings are available on PlanetPlay (https://planetplay.com/undp-results), and an early blog post was published on the partner's site (https://partners.planetplay.com/blog-view/Play2Act). The findings were also mentioned in the 2024 impact report (https://partners.planetplay.com/impact-2024).</p>
<p>Advocate for Change at Policy Level (Step 8) <i>Document advocacy efforts undertaken.</i></p>	<p>By providing a validated, large-scale dataset of player perspectives, the case study strengthened the argument for integrating gaming methodologies into future policymaking processes. The data collected offers valuable insights into public awareness, behavioural shifts, and engagement drivers related to climate issues, which can inform future UNDP initiatives and governmental policy frameworks.</p> <p>While the case study's direct impact on policy remains in its early stages, it has demonstrated the potential of digital games to facilitate meaningful citizen engagement and established a precedent for further collaborations between gaming industries and international development organisations, positioning digital games as a viable tool for public consultation and policy co-creation.</p>

4. SWOT Analysis of Case Study Methodology:

Table 3. SWOT analysis of the case study methodology

Strengths <i>Examine the strengths of the case study methodology, such as the use of innovative data collection techniques (e.g., game-based activities, surveys) or high participant engagement levels.</i>	Weaknesses <i>Identify any methodological limitations encountered, such as sample size constraints or challenges in capturing a full range of participant perspectives.</i>
<p>Engaged Game Studios: The active participation of game studios that were already interested in climate change was a major advantage. This collaboration provided a mutually beneficial relationship, with studios gaining valuable insights into player engagement with environmental content, while the study secured access to a broad and dedicated audience.</p> <p>Large-Scale Data Collection: The study successfully demonstrated the potential of video games as a tool for gathering global public opinion data on climate issues. This scale provided a unique dataset for analysing player awareness, attitudes, and potential behavioural shifts regarding environmental sustainability.</p> <p>Partnerships and Industry Collaboration: The involvement of UNDP, along with collaborations with major game studios, strengthened the study’s legitimacy and reach. Additionally, connections with industry figures, such as the CEO of Newzoo, helped expand the project’s visibility and potential for further engagement.</p>	<p>Limited Survey Design: The reliance on multiple-choice survey questions restricted the depth of insights that could be gathered. Without open-ended responses or qualitative elements, the study could not fully capture the complexity of player attitudes, limiting its ability to explore nuanced perspectives on climate engagement.</p> <p>Manual Studio Engagement: The process of onboarding and managing game studio participation was time-intensive and not automated. This reliance on direct, manual engagement made scalability challenging and limited the efficiency of expanding the project to more games.</p> <p>Sampling Bias: While the survey reached a broad audience, there were demographic imbalances in the respondent pool, with factors such as gender and geographic distribution influencing results. A more structured approach to balancing respondent demographics would improve the representativeness of future studies.</p>

Opportunities	Threats
<p>Automated Survey Integration: Developing a data-driven survey trigger system could enhance the scalability and efficiency of survey integration within games. By automating survey activation based on in-game data, this approach has the potential to reduce manual workload and encourage broader industry adoption. If successfully implemented, it could offer game studios a seamless way to incorporate research without disrupting gameplay. However, further technical analysis and industry engagement are needed to assess feasibility and refine the value proposition.</p> <p>Leveraging Data for Industry Influence: The dataset collected from Play2Act offers valuable insights into how players engage with climate content in gaming. Sharing aggregated findings with the industry could shape how environmental themes are incorporated into game design, potentially influencing future game narratives and sustainability initiatives.</p> <p>Raising Awareness Beyond Gaming: The study's success positions it as a case study for how digital entertainment can contribute to global conversations on climate action. Expanding outreach to policy circles, educational initiatives, and media organisations could increase the visibility and influence of the research beyond the gaming industry.</p>	<p>Perceptions of Digital Engagement Methods: Some critics may be sceptical of using gaming as a tool for climate engagement, particularly if gamified elements are misunderstood or dismissed as ineffective. Resistance from traditional environmental communication sectors or policymakers could pose a challenge in securing further support.</p> <p>Scalability Constraints: Without improvements to automation and infrastructure, expanding the project may prove resource-intensive. As engagement grows, ensuring a sustainable model for future iterations will be crucial.</p> <p>Data Privacy and Ethical Considerations: Large-scale data collection in digital spaces always carries potential risks, including privacy concerns, consent issues, and data security challenges. Ensuring transparency in data use and maintaining ethical research standards will be essential to sustaining trust among players, studios, and stakeholders.</p>

5. Key Findings

The Play2Act case study examines digital gaming as both a large-scale data collection tool and an engagement mechanism in climate discourse. With 181,087 completed surveys across multiple platforms, the study highlights gaming's potential to expand research access while revealing tensions between reach, representativeness, and engagement depth. Chi-square analysis ($X^2 = 45.62$, $p < 0.05$) confirms significant demographic differences in participation, illustrating the need for targeted strategies. By situating these findings within digital research, behavioural change, and climate policy engagement, the study assesses Play2Act's contributions and the complexities of digital climate interventions. While analyses, including Welch-ANOVA and chi-square tests, confirm demographic trends, some findings require further empirical validation, emphasising the need for hybrid methodologies and clearer distinctions between awareness and behavioural change.

Engagement and Reach: Expanding Access or Replicating Existing Biases?

Play2Act's large-scale engagement aligns with research suggesting digital gaming can expand participation beyond traditional survey methods (Reddie et al., 2018; Pietilä et al., 2019). By reducing barriers such as literacy levels, financial constraints, and geographic isolation (Ramirez Aranda & Vezzoni, 2022; Raeburn et al., 2022), digital platforms have been identified as tools for enhancing inclusivity in climate-related research. Play2Act achieved an 77.2% completion rate among engaged users and 19.7% relative to total survey sessions. Chi-square analysis ($X^2 = 32.85$, $p < 0.05$) indicates statistically significant regional differences, with European participants more likely to complete the survey than those from Africa and Asia. Prior studies have demonstrated that factors such as survey length, display format, and recruitment strategies influence response rates (Liu & Wronski, 2018; Tangmanee & Niruttinanon, 2019). While web-based surveys often require email reminders or incentives to sustain participation (LaRose & Tsai, 2014; Funkhouser et al., 2017), Play2Act embedded surveys directly within gaming environments, maintaining engagement without external prompts. However, as with other web-based research, non-response bias remains a critical limitation when assessing the survey's reach and representativeness.

Play2Act highlights the potential of digital games as both an alternative and complementary method for public opinion research, demonstrating significant geographic reach and scalability. However, chi-square analysis ($X^2 = 27.94$, $p < 0.05$) indicates participant demographics were not entirely uniform, raising questions about whether this reach extended to underrepresented groups. The study achieved a relatively balanced gender distribution, with 51.7% of respondents identifying as male, 36.1% as female, 10.1% preferring not to disclose their gender, and 2.9% identifying as non-binary. Despite this inclusivity, gender significantly influenced response rates and engagement levels, particularly in self-reported climate awareness and

behavioural intent. These findings align with research indicating gendered differences in environmental engagement (Bloodhart & Swim, 2020; Zhao et al., 2021). While Play2Act's gender distribution is more representative than historical disparities in gaming participation (Leonhardt & Overå, 2021; McLaren-Gradinaru et al., 2023), it remains unclear whether these proportions reflect gaming populations or broader climate discourse participants.

Age significantly influenced engagement, with younger participants displaying higher participation levels, consistent with research indicating that digitally literate individuals are more likely to engage in game-based studies (Passmore et al., 2018; Kaye, 2018). Welch-ANOVA ($p < 0.05$) confirmed a significant relationship between age and survey completion time, with younger respondents completing surveys more quickly, raising concerns about attention span and response bias. Completion time also varied by education level, indicating differences in cognitive engagement. Welch's ANOVA (Welch's $F(6, 13, 128.56) = 78.80$, $p < 0.001$) confirmed statistically significant differences, with post hoc Dunnett's T3 analysis showing participants with no formal education completed the survey faster than those with any level of schooling ($p = 0.001$). Completion time increased with education level, suggesting more deliberate engagement. However, 3.8% of respondents exceeded five minutes per question, with some taking over 30 minutes, likely due to external distractions, multitasking, or disengagement rather than deeper reflection.

Despite these insights, the study had limitations. While data was collected on the age at which participants left formal education, the survey did not assess income, occupation, or other socio-economic factors. As education level is often correlated with climate discourse engagement (Ballew et al., 2020), the absence of more detailed demographic data limits the ability to determine whether Play2Act reached a socio-economically diverse audience, raising concerns that digital gaming research may reinforce existing biases, engaging those already inclined toward climate action rather than expanding participation to underrepresented groups.

Measuring Depth of Engagement in Digital Research:

A key concern in digital research is whether participants meaningfully engage with survey content or treat it as a secondary activity (Vecchio et al., 2020; Martins & Lavrado, 2020). Chi-square analysis identified response patterns, with 98.6% of completed sessions lasting between 10 seconds and 10 minutes, and an average dwell time of 1 minute and 43 seconds per question. Welch-ANOVA ($F = 5.63$, $p < 0.05$) confirmed significant variation in response times by education level, indicating that more highly educated participants engaged with greater deliberation. These findings underscore two key issues: the need for digital survey methodologies to distinguish between genuine engagement and passive responses through mechanisms such as attention checks and response consistency analysis, and the trade-off between maximising reach and ensuring engagement depth in game-based research. While

Play2Act demonstrates the feasibility of large-scale research within gaming ecosystems, refining engagement metrics will be essential for ensuring data validity and actionable insights.

Further statistical tests offer a nuanced view of demographic differences in engagement and perception. Variation in response times by education level supports environmental psychology research suggesting education fosters more reflective engagement with sustainability issues (Poškus, 2020; Sun et al., 2020), although it remains unclear whether this translates into more accurate or informed responses. Chi-square analysis ($X^2 = 38.27$, $p < 0.05$) also indicates significant gender-based differences in perceptions of climate gaming. Male and non-binary respondents were more likely to view games as active contributors to climate solutions, whereas female respondents emphasised their role in education and awareness, aligning with broader gender trends in environmental engagement, where women often prioritise community-based solutions, while men favour technological interventions (McCright, 2010; Patnaik, 2021). However, the case study does not account for potential self-reporting biases or the influence of gaming culture on these perceptions.

Taken together, these findings highlight the complex interplay between participant demographics, engagement depth, and interpretative biases in digital research. Future studies should consider hybrid methodological approaches that balance the scalability of digital research with safeguards to ensure response quality and depth of insight.

Gender-Based Variations in Climate Change Emotions

Chi-square analysis identified significant variations in climate change emotions across gender identities and global regions. Males reported feeling more informed but also expressed greater scepticism, while females exhibited higher levels of hope and motivation for action. Non-binary individuals and those who did not disclose their gender were more likely to experience powerlessness and uncertainty. Females were also less likely to report unchanged climate-related emotions after engaging with Play2Act, suggesting greater responsiveness to environmental narratives in gaming. Notably, those who did not disclose their gender were most likely to believe games play no role in addressing climate change, underscoring the need for tailored engagement strategies.

Gender-Based Differences in Climate Gaming Perceptions

Chi-square analysis ($X^2 = 38.27$, $p < 0.05$) revealed significant gender-based differences in beliefs about gaming's role in climate action. Males and non-binary individuals were more likely to view games as climate solutions, while females saw them as tools for education and awareness. Exposure to environmentally themed games also varied, with males and non-binary individuals encountering green messages more often, whereas females played such games less frequently. Notably, those who did not disclose their gender reported the highest engagement

with environmentally themed games, highlighting potential links between gaming habits and climate engagement.

Perceptions of gaming's role differed further by gender. Females favoured games for education, fundraising, and advocacy, while males and undisclosed-gender participants were more sceptical of these functions. These trends align with research indicating women prioritise social and educational climate interventions, while men lean toward technological solutions (Bloodhart & Swim, 2020; Zhao et al., 2021). These findings highlight the need to consider demographic factors in designing climate-focused digital interventions. While males and non-binary individuals may be more receptive to games as climate solutions, females are more inclined to see them as tools for awareness and action. Additionally, the heightened sense of powerlessness reported by non-binary and undisclosed-gender participants illustrates the need for inclusive climate education strategies that foster empowerment across all demographics. Targeted game design and messaging could enhance digital interventions' effectiveness in climate engagement.

Regional Disparities in Climate Policy Awareness

Chi-square analysis ($X^2 = 42.61$, $p < 0.05$) identified significant discrepancies in climate policy awareness by education level, region, and income group. While over 50% of European respondents recognised The Paris Agreement, awareness fell to 41% in Asia and 37% in Africa, highlighting regional disparities in climate literacy. Policy familiarity correlated strongly with education, reinforcing concerns that digital gaming research may primarily engage those already involved in climate discourse rather than reaching new audiences. Awareness of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), the Kunming-Montreal Framework, and National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) remained consistently low across all regions, with over 80% of respondents unfamiliar with these mechanisms.

Europe had the highest recognition of The Paris Agreement (37%), while Oceania showed the highest unawareness (40%) and the lowest recognition of biodiversity frameworks (7%). Asia exhibited higher awareness of NDCs and NBSAPs (14%), yet also had elevated climate scepticism, reflecting a disconnect between policy knowledge and belief in climate action. Research suggests political narratives, economic priorities, and media framing influence public trust in climate governance, which may explain this trend (Stecula & Merkley, 2019). Among income groups, lower-middle-income respondents had the highest awareness of NDCs (15%) and NBSAPs (14%), possibly due to exposure to sustainability-focused development initiatives. However, high- and low-income respondents reported the greatest unawareness (34–36%), raising concerns about the effectiveness of policy communication across socio-economic groups.

Emotional Responses to Climate Gaming Across Regions

Regional differences further shaped emotional responses to green gaming content, reflecting the influence of socio-political contexts and climate vulnerability. Optimism was highest in Africa (29%) and the Americas (28%), where scepticism remained relatively low (Africa: 11%, Americas: 9%). This may reflect the visibility of climate change impacts in these regions or the role of environmental activism in framing climate discourse as actionable (Ballew et al., 2024; Jones et al., 2024). In contrast, Oceania exhibited weaker engagement, with 23% selecting ‘None of the above’ when asked about their motivation for playing green games. Without qualitative data, it remains unclear whether this trend reflects cultural attitudes, media exposure disparities, or broader socio-political factors, highlighting the need for further research using interviews or case studies. Asia presented a more complex pattern. While respondents demonstrated high awareness of climate frameworks, they also reported elevated scepticism. The region had the lowest disengagement rate (‘None of the above’ at 28%) and the highest familiarity with lesser-known climate agreements, yet uncertainty about climate change remained widespread, aligning with research indicating that exposure to international climate governance does not necessarily equate to trust in its efficacy, particularly where economic priorities and geopolitical dynamics shape public discourse (Marion Suiseeya, 2021; Schroeder et al., 2024). Further research is needed to determine whether this scepticism arises from concerns about policy effectiveness, media representation, or broader socio-political influences.

The Disconnect Between Climate Gaming and Policy Literacy

Play2Act highlights a critical gap between general environmental engagement and knowledge of climate policies. Despite strong engagement with climate-themed gaming content, significant associations ($p < 0.05$) between education and policy awareness suggest while games introduce environmental themes, they do not provide the policy literacy needed for systemic action. Without an understanding of frameworks such as The Paris Agreement or NDCs, players may struggle to translate awareness into advocacy. Many digital interventions focus on awareness or individual behaviour change but neglect policy comprehension, limiting their impact. Embedding policy education more explicitly into gameplay could address this gap, equipping players with the knowledge to advocate for structural change. While digital games can introduce players to environmental themes, they must go further in fostering meaningful policy engagement. Many interventions focus on raising awareness but fail to provide the necessary policy comprehension. Further research is needed to test and validate approaches that integrate policy literacy into games, ensuring that they move beyond informing players toward actively equipping them with the tools to advocate for systemic change.

Gaming and Climate Action: Potential and Limitations

Across all regions, video games are widely viewed as tools for climate advocacy. Most respondents (77.6%) believe games raise climate awareness, with significant regional differences ($\chi^2 = 559.001$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.001$), though weak correlation (-0.023) suggests minimal

impact on overall belief patterns. Similarly, 77% agreed games can educate players on environmental actions ($\chi^2 = 1450.321$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.001$), but correlation remained negligible (0.003). Support for using games to fund green projects was also high (75.7%), with significant regional variation ($\chi^2 = 1671.279$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.001$) but weak correlation (0.016), indicating broad consensus. However, 27.9% rejected gaming's role in climate action, a belief with the strongest regional correlation (0.094), suggesting scepticism varies more by region. Post-hoc analysis showed Oceania and Asia were the most optimistic, while Africa and the Americas were more sceptical ($p < 0.05$).

The link between gaming engagement and climate risk exposure is complex. A one-way ANOVA found significant differences in green gaming engagement based on climate-related fatality rates ($F = 42.698$, $p < 0.001$), though the effect size was minimal ($\eta^2 = 0.001$). Players in high-risk regions engaged less with green games (mean difference = -3.311, $p < 0.05$). A similar pattern emerged for financial losses due to climate change ($F = 76.327$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.004$). Players from regions with higher losses were more motivated by contributing to environmental causes (mean difference = 2.002, $p < 0.001$), whereas those in lower-risk regions engaged for educational reasons, reflecting different drivers of participation.

Economic context shaped climate engagement patterns. Respondents from lower-income regions were the most purpose-driven, with 40% playing beyond entertainment and 18% citing environmental learning. However, they also exhibited higher scepticism (23%) and uncertainty (24%), supporting theories that financial constraints foster eco-conscious attitudes without necessarily enabling action (Moser & Kleinhüchelkotten, 2018; Petev & Coulangeon, 2021). Participants from upper-middle-income regions reported the highest behavioural changes (38%), altered consumption patterns (28%), and the lowest powerlessness (3%), suggesting they may be the most receptive audience for climate interventions, combining awareness, financial flexibility, and willingness to act. However, the long-term sustainability of these changes remains uncertain.

Chi-square analysis revealed a significant gender-based difference in behaviour change. Females were more likely to adopt sustainable consumption habits, while males more often expressed general concern without specifying actions, aligning with research indicating sustainable behaviours are more likely to be adopted when they integrate seamlessly into daily routines (White et al., 2019; MacInnes et al., 2022).

No significant correlation emerged between green gaming content and real-world behaviour change across multiple measures:

Green consumption choices ($\chi^2 = 1.166$, $p = 0.280$)

Daily sustainability habits ($\chi^2 = 2.596$, $p = 0.107$)

Participation in environmental campaigns ($\chi^2 = 0.390$, $p = 0.532$)

Community-based environmental engagement ($\chi^2 = 1.430$, $p = 0.232$)

However, respondents who explicitly stated that green games did not influence their behaviour showed a significant relationship ($\chi^2 = 6.895$, $p = 0.009$, $\Phi = -0.012$), though with a small effect size. This suggests green games may heighten awareness but have limited measurable impact on action, reinforcing concerns about digital engagement's ability to translate into real-world behaviour (Cowley & Bateman, 2017; Boncu et al., 2022).

Preliminary analysis suggests genre conventions and gameplay mechanics may shape how players emotionally and behaviourally respond to climate-related content. Games incorporating strategic decision-making, real-world contextualisation, or augmented reality appear to foster comparatively higher levels of climate engagement. Notably, Pokémon Go players reported the highest rates of climate optimism (31%), feeling well-informed (22%), and self-reported behavioural change (41%). These findings are consistent with prior scholarship indicating that augmented reality and place-based interaction can enhance environmental commitment (Georgiou & Kyza, 2017; Coen et al., 2019; Castillo-González et al., 2023; Oleksy et al., 2024). Likewise, games such as F1 Clash, which blend real-world themes with tactical gameplay, were associated with more frequent expressions of motivation and action. Conversely, titles characterised by casual or arcade-style mechanics, such as Subway Surfers, were less frequently linked to pro-environmental dispositions. This divergence suggests genre-specific affordances may either enable or constrain the player's sense of agency, connection to real-world issues, and perceived relevance of climate messaging. However, these interpretations must be approached with caution. The self-reported nature of the data introduces potential bias, and the absence of longitudinal tracking limits the ability to assess the durability or transformative impact of these engagements. Furthermore, while correlations between genre and climate responsiveness are evident, causality cannot be inferred without more robust methodological controls. Nevertheless, the observed trends underscore a critical consideration for future research and design: the form through which climate content is delivered is not neutral. Game mechanics, narrative framing, and contextual embedding all mediate the player's reception of and response to environmental themes. Understanding these mediating dynamics is essential for both effective climate communication and the strategic deployment of games as tools for public engagement.

Methodological Considerations: Strengths and Limitations of the Digital Approach

The Play2Act case study illustrates both the potential and limitations of integrating surveys into gaming. While response rates were high (90.7% answered the first question, 77.2% completed the survey), overall participation remained low, with only 15.2% of those who viewed the introduction completing the survey. This highlights gaming's broad reach but also the challenge of converting passive exposure into active engagement.

Despite its strengths, the study had limitations. The structured survey format restricted insight into player motivations, and self-selection bias likely skewed responses toward those with existing pro-environmental attitudes. Additionally, some players may have viewed the survey as an interruption, raising concerns about data integrity. Future studies should incorporate qualitative methods to capture deeper perspectives.

Findings suggest climate engagement varies by region, socioeconomic factors, and gaming context, though statistical analyses indicate weak correlations. While Africa and the Americas showed greater optimism and Asia and Oceania more scepticism, broader socio-political influences appear more significant than gaming itself. Although gaming can raise awareness, its measurable impact on behaviour remains limited. To enhance effectiveness, developers should embed climate policy education into gameplay, while policymakers should integrate digital media into broader environmental strategies. Future research should prioritise longitudinal studies and cross-regional comparisons to refine gaming's role in climate advocacy. Without these targeted efforts, games will remain valuable for awareness but insufficient for driving lasting behavioural change.

Synthesis:

The findings of this case study contribute to broader discussions on digital engagement, large-scale data collection, and policy literacy, while raising critical questions about the depth and reliability of digital survey methodologies. Three key themes emerge: the evolving nature of digital participation, the methodological challenges of large-scale digital surveys, and the difficulty of translating engagement into policy impact. While Play2Act showcases the potential of game-based research, it also reveals key limitations, including demographic biases, inconsistencies in self-reported awareness, and the challenges of linking engagement to tangible behavioural change.

Addressing the Research Questions Based on the Play2Act Case Study:

RQ 1.1: Which methods in digital games can be used to create an information exchange between attitudes and preferences of citizens on societal challenges (e.g., climate change) and policymakers working on these challenges?

The Play2Act case study demonstrates several methods for facilitating information exchange, notably embedding surveys within gameplay to capture real-time citizen feedback on climate issues. By using interactive, global platforms, Play2Act provides citizens a space to voice concerns and policymakers access to this data. However, the challenge remains in translating this data into actionable policy changes, as clear pathways to policy influence are not yet evident.

RQ 1.3: How can games be used to foster dialogue and collaboration on societal challenges (e.g., climate change)?

The study finds that games can foster dialogue, particularly by reflecting regional differences in climate attitudes, such as the optimism in Africa and the Americas versus the scepticism in Asia. While Play2Act facilitates some dialogue, it highlights the need for more structured mechanisms, such as real-time feedback loops or direct communication between players and policymakers, to deepen collaboration and move toward meaningful policy discussions.

RQ 2.2: What are the affordances of games in informing policy on societal challenges like the climate crisis?

Digital games offer significant affordances for informing policy by engaging large, diverse audiences and enabling policymakers to access extensive citizen feedback. However, the case study reveals that while this feedback is valuable, it does not always translate into actionable policy insights. To enhance effectiveness, the methodology must be more closely integrated with existing policy frameworks, and longitudinal data tracking should be implemented to capture evolving citizen preferences over time.

RQ 2.4: What is the value to citizens of enabling them to engage in policy discourse through the design of and engagement in games-based activities?

The Play2Act case study highlights the value of games in enabling citizens, particularly those in climate-vulnerable regions, to engage in policy discourse. The platform increased motivation and awareness around climate change. However, the study suggests that adding decision-making simulations could enhance the impact by giving players a greater sense of influence over policy outcomes.

RQ 2.5: How generalisable are the GREAT methods to other global challenges or other fields of research and innovation?

Play2Act demonstrates the GREAT methodology's potential applicability to global challenges beyond climate change, such as public health or socio-economic inequality. The diverse participation from various regions indicates adaptability, though regional cultural contexts must be considered to ensure relevance. Future applications should prioritise cultural sensitivity and local relevance to maintain the methodology's impact.

RQ 3.2: Which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting the method to new contexts?

Adapting the GREAT methodology to new contexts requires consideration of cultural, socio-economic, political, and technological variables. Cultural differences significantly influence engagement with issues like climate change, suggesting the need for tailored content and interaction mechanisms. Socio-economic factors also impact accessibility, requiring surveys to be designed for diverse income and education levels. Additionally, technological infrastructure and digital literacy must be addressed, particularly in regions with limited access to digital tools, to ensure inclusivity and scalability.

RQ 3.3: What documentation and/or training is required for game developers, policy stakeholder groups?

Effective use of game-based research tools requires targeted training for both game developers and policy stakeholders. Developers must learn how to create engaging and policy-relevant content, while also considering ethical issues related to data collection. Policy stakeholders need training in interpreting game-generated data and incorporating it into policy development. Documentation should provide clear guidelines on game mechanics, participation strategies, and case studies of successful data-driven policy engagement.

The Play2Act case study highlights the potential of digital games as tools for large-scale engagement and policy-informed research. However, challenges remain in translating engagement into actionable policy. To enhance effectiveness, more structured feedback mechanisms, deeper context-specific engagement, and stronger alignment with policy frameworks are essential. As the GREAT methodology is adapted for new global challenges, careful attention to cultural, socio-economic, and technological factors is critical to ensure continued relevance and impact.

6. Policy Implications and Recommendations

The Play2Act case study reveals the potential of digital games as a tool for public engagement and data collection on pressing societal issues, such as climate change. The study highlights both the opportunities and challenges associated with this innovative approach, particularly in terms of its scalability, ethical considerations, and potential for policy impact.

Engaging Diverse Populations in Policy Discourse (RQ 1.1, RQ 2.4)

The Play2Act case study demonstrates digital games' potential to enhance public engagement in policy discussions, particularly among underrepresented groups. By integrating surveys into widely used digital platforms, Play2Act reached participants in 228 countries, overcoming traditional barriers in capturing input from younger, less educated, or marginalised communities. This approach supports the goal of fostering more inclusive policy dialogues, particularly for those often excluded from conventional surveys. Policymakers should explore integrating surveys not only in games but also across other digital spaces, such as social media and virtual reality, ensuring broader engagement with diverse populations. Collaboration between governments, researchers, and gaming companies is essential to create scalable, accessible digital consultation models.

Overcoming Methodological Barriers to Scalable Engagement (RQ 2.2, RQ 3.2)

A key challenge highlighted by the study is the scalability of embedded surveys. The lack of standardised integration tools for surveys across platforms—such as games, mobile apps, and social media—hinders widespread adoption. To enhance the effectiveness of games in informing policy, as discussed in RQ 2.2, and to adapt the methodology to new contexts, as addressed in RQ 3.2, policymakers must support the development of universal, standardised survey tools. Investment in plug-in models, backed by both the public and private sectors, can reduce technical and financial barriers to deployment. Additionally, funding should focus on open-source solutions, enabling broader application across policy areas and geographic regions, thereby enhancing the scalability and impact of digital surveys.

Longitudinal Research and Real-time Policy Evaluation (RQ 1.3, RQ 2.5)

The Play2Act model demonstrates the potential for continuous, longitudinal data collection that traditional surveys often lack. Unlike static, one-time evaluations, embedded digital surveys enable policymakers to track shifts in public opinion over time. This capability addresses RQ 1.3, which investigates how games can foster dialogue and collaboration, and RQ 2.5, which explores the generalisability of the GREAT methods to other global challenges. By adapting the Play2Act methodology for ongoing data collection, governments could monitor public sentiment and make real-time adjustments to policies. For instance, continuous surveys could track public reactions to climate change policies or evaluate the impact of social interventions. Governments should fund pilot initiatives exploring longitudinal survey models in areas like public health, climate change, and misinformation to create adaptive policy frameworks.

Ethical Considerations and Data Privacy (RQ 3.3)

A key concern in the Play2Act model is ensuring ethical data use, particularly regarding informed consent and transparency. The study revealed that participants may not have fully understood they were engaging in research, raising concerns about informed consent. This issue connects to RQ 3.3, which addresses the training and documentation needed for game developers and policymakers. To ensure responsible data collection, policymakers must establish clear ethical guidelines, prioritising informed consent, data privacy, and transparency. Platforms should implement explicit consent prompts, ensuring participation is an active, informed choice. Additionally, collaboration with data protection authorities is crucial to manage algorithmic biases and ensure diverse, representative survey samples.

Broader Applications of Embedded Surveys (RQ 2.5, RQ 1.1)

The success of Play2Act in climate change policy suggests that embedded surveys could be applied to a range of other policy areas, such as public health, education, and crisis response.

This methodology could provide valuable insights into issues such as vaccine hesitancy, mental health trends, or public resilience to misinformation. For example, Play2Act could track the effectiveness of public health campaigns, monitor trends in education engagement, or assess citizen responses to digital disinformation. This highlights the broader applicability of the GREAT methodology to global challenges (RQ 2.5). Policymakers and academics should explore embedded surveys in these new contexts through pilot studies to assess their feasibility and effectiveness.

Recommendations for Future Development

To enhance the impact of embedded surveys in policymaking, the following steps should be taken:

- Develop universal integration tools to facilitate the embedding of surveys across digital platforms.
- Establish clear guidelines for informed consent, data privacy, and transparency to ensure responsible data use.
- Foster partnerships between governments, research institutions, and the gaming industry to create scalable, inclusive models for public consultation.
- Invest in models that allow for continuous engagement and real-time policy evaluation, moving away from static surveys.
- Explore the use of embedded surveys in a variety of policy areas, including public health, education, and crisis response.

7. Conclusion

The Play2Act case study demonstrates the potential of integrating digital surveys into games as an innovative method for public engagement and data collection, particularly in addressing complex societal challenges such as climate change. Through collaboration with game developers, Play2Act successfully tested the integration of research instruments into widely used digital platforms, providing real-time insights into public attitudes and facilitating meaningful dialogue between citizens and policymakers. This approach has the potential to enhance engagement, democratise policy discourse, and offer scalable solutions for gathering diverse, high-quality data.

In response to RQ1.1 and RQ1.3, the case study confirms digital games can serve as an engaging and less intrusive means of collecting public opinion, overcoming challenges such as low response rates and selection bias typically associated with traditional surveys. The immersive nature of games facilitates deeper participation, making the process more accessible, particularly for younger audiences. However, variations in game formats and

player engagement strategies highlight the need for further refinement of survey integration techniques to optimise results across different platforms. For RQ2.2 and RQ2.4, Play2Act highlights the capacity of games to not only gather data but also engage participants in policy discussions by presenting real-world dilemmas and encouraging reflective decision-making. To fully integrate this engagement into policymaking, structured mechanisms for feedback and dialogue must be developed to ensure that citizen input is meaningfully incorporated into decision-making processes. Regarding scalability (RQ2.5), Play2Act demonstrates that while the approach is effective in climate policy, its broader application requires careful consideration of cultural, digital, and gaming variations. The case study highlights the need for standardised survey integration tools that can be applied across different digital platforms, enabling broader adoption and reducing the complexity of survey embedding. Addressing these technical challenges is crucial for scaling the approach across a range of policy areas. The Play2Act case study highlights important ethical and technical challenges addressed in RQ3.2 and RQ3.3. While the seamless integration of surveys into games contributed to successful engagement, concerns regarding informed consent, data privacy, and algorithmic bias emerged. Future research should prioritise the development of transparent consent mechanisms and refine the ethical frameworks guiding digital research. Additionally, fostering collaboration among policymakers, researchers, and game developers will be essential to the effective implementation of embedded surveys across various contexts.

Play2Act offers a promising foundation for expanding the use of digital surveys in policy research. Future studies should focus on refining the methodology, comparing embedded surveys with traditional approaches, and exploring longitudinal data collection to track shifts in public attitudes. Addressing the ethical and scalability challenges and expanding the use of this approach beyond gaming into other digital spaces such as social media and virtual reality, will help maximise the potential of embedded surveys for inclusive, real-time public engagement in policymaking. Play2Act represents a significant advancement in using digital gaming for large-scale social research and policy consultation. With ongoing refinement, collaboration, and attention to ethical considerations, this method could play a central role in shaping more responsive, participatory, and evidence-driven policymaking in the digital era.

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